

A CASE STUDY OF CHILD LABOUR AS A MAJOR PROBLEMS IN SLUMS AREA

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Abstract

Slum as a part of many urban settlements which can always affect the urban environment of nearby location. Most of the people of slum area work on any occupational system of nearby localities. They may work as driver, watchmen, wage labour, garbage collector, hotel waiter , and so on many think the working population include child labour. Because of some reasons it is therefore one of the basic problem of slum in many urban areas.

This paper is basically made to study the problems of child labour in Ganesh Nagar and Ajanta Nagar slum of Pimpri Chinchwad urban area. The study was carrying out on the basis of primary data collection with the help of questionnaires of slum dwellers, and secondary data from Municipal Corporation and other offices.

Introduction:

The growth of slums in urban area is one of the major issues for urban development authority. The definition of “slum” varies from country to country. In India, each state has its own definition of slum. The National Definition of ‘Slum areas’ was set by the Slum Areas Improvement and Clearance act of 1956. It defines them as places where buildings: are in any respect unfit for human habitation; are by reason of dilapidation, overcrowding, faulty arrangement and design of such buildings, narrowness or faulty arrangement of streets, lack of

ventilation, light, sanitation facilities or any combination of these factors which are detrimental to safety, health and morals.

The physical problems manifest themselves in the form of open drains, disorganized layout of structures and roads and apathy in the disposal of garbage. Social or human problems include lack of privacy, imminent conflicts which are bound to arise when people are in close proximity, almost impinging on the space of each other and a related sense of insecurity. The occasional brawls that take place may lead to Law and Order problems at times. The vulnerability of slum population to indulge in petty crimes and take umbrage in the 'politically secure' environment can also not be ruled out and the dense, impenetrable population clusters of almost homogenous groups provide an ideal set-up for this. On the economic front, the slum Population is apparently the most marginalized. Some of them survive on a shoe-string budget or even a hand to mouth existence, though cases of relative opulence hidden in an ocean of poverty cannot be ruled out. However, generally the slum population is below the poverty line.

Children are the gifts; they are the precious gifts presented by Almighty God to human life for filling the world with smile, happiness, and hope. Children are the future citizens; it is childhood which determines a child's future, his/her life and their worthy contributions to the world. Thus it becomes an important aspect for us, for everyone in the society, and for the Government to protect, nourish and work for the overall welfare of children of a particular Nation and the children of the World as a whole. The issue of child labor, especially the rising number of urban child workers, is being increasingly seen as a global problem. Child workers in urban areas mainly include the children of rural migrants who come to the city in search of a livelihood as well as children who are homeless or orphans. Children mostly work in trade and services, followed by other sectors such as slum-based small manufacturing, construction and domestic help. Some of the important aspects of urban child labor include the lack of education and nutrition, criminalization of children and proliferation of the gang culture, and the physical and sexual abuse of children

When we discuss about child labour, we know that it is a curse upon the God gifted little ones on Earth. Child labour, in general, means the employment of children in any work with or without payment. Every child out of school in the age group of 5 to 14 years, children who are

paid in work, children who work outside the homes or children who in hazardous industries can be said to be child laborers. According to Stein and Davies, child labour means any work by children that interferes with their full physical development, the opportunities for a desirable minimum education and for their needed recreation.

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Study Area:

The existence of slums can be traced back to the decade of industrialization in Pimpri Chinchwad. Slums have proliferated as a corollary of industrial growth in the area. The first slum survey carried out by the Municipal Council in 1976 identified 35 slum pockets (5621 hutments) with a population of 26,470. The slums were located chiefly around the industries on open lands close to the workplaces. The survey was updated by PCMC in 1987 when 65 slum pockets (21326 hutments) with a population of 96,272 persons were identified. Further, in 2002, the Government under its resolution dated 11/07/2001, carried out a slum survey which identified 71 slum pockets (35412 hutments) with a population of 1,46,054 persons.

The city of Pimpri- Chinchwad is situated near the western margin of the Deccan Plateau on the leeward side of the Sahyadri ranges and Western Ghats, 560 m above sea level, on the banks of the rivers Mula, Pawana and Indrayani. The city is located on $18^{\circ} 37' 0''$ N Latitude and $73^{\circ} 48' 0''$ E Longitude.

Selected Slum Pockets

Ajanta Nagar in Akurdi-(19413 sq.mt.)

The Ajanta Nagar is Located at $18^{\circ}39'46''$ N Latitude and $73^{\circ}47'30''$ E Longitude & Elevation From sea Level is 604 mt.

Ganesh Nagar in Pimpri- (2429sq.mt.)

The Ganesh Nagar is Located at 18°36'45" N Latitude and 73°48'17" E Longitude & Elevation is 570 mt. From MSL in the Pimpri urban area.

Hypothesis:-

The basic foundation of research work is based on the hypothesis. It is a pre-supposition of research work to be carried out on a particular problem. The systematic study of the present problem will be carried out on the basis of following hypothesis.

“Child labour affects to socio-economic development”

The Hypotheses focuses on aspects related to slum Population by analyzing the deterioration of environment due to occurrence of slums.

Objectives of study:-

1. The study school going children.
2. The comparative analysis of child worker in Ganesh Nagar & Ajanta Nagar slum pockets.
3. The study of Reasons for child being involved in work.

Data base & methodology:-

Following points will be the scheduled system of to be applied for this research Papers.

a) Reference works:

(1) Books and Journals. (2) Internet and Newspapers (3) Google and Wikimapia.

b) Primary data sources:

1) Field visit, observation. 2) Questionnaires & interviews 3) photographs.

Understanding the concept of child labour:

There is no universally accepted definition of “child labor.”

"Child labor" is, generally speaking, work for children that harms them or exploits them in some way (physically, mentally, morally, or by blocking access to education).

Child: A child (in the context of child labor) is a person who has not completed fifteenth year of age as yet.

Child Labor (Prohibition & Regulation) Act: This is an Act of the Government of India that spells out the definition of child labor and penalties prescribed for violators. This Act came into force on 23rd December 1986.

Child Labor/ Working Child: “Child labour” is a narrower concept than “economically active children”, excluding all those children aged 12 years and older who are working only a few hours a week in permitted light work and those aged 15 years and above whose work is not classified as “hazardous”. The concept of “child labour” adopted by the ILO Minimum Age Convention, 1973 (No. 138) represents the most comprehensive and authoritative international definition of minimum age for admission to employment or work, implying “economic activity”.

Historical Review of problem:

History of child labour can be traced to some dark realms of industrialisation. But a more detailed study of this heinous, shameful practice can reveal that child labour was there much before industrialisation in various forms like in child slavery. If we turn the pages of History we see that there was a custom for youths from the Mediterranean basin to serve as aides, charioteers and armed bearers to their adult counterparts. A few of such examples can be found in Bibles when David serves his King Soul; we find the examples of Hercules and Hylash in Greek Mythology as well. In Greece this practice was considered to be an educational tradition and boys were considered to be an efficient fighting force. Hitler Youth was an official organization in the Nazi Army. During the battle of Berlin, this youth force was a major part of the German Defenses.

In India, children used to help and accompany their parents in agricultural and other household activities in ancient times. Thus we see that child labour is not quite a new thing to the world.

But during 1780 and 1840s, there was a massive increase in child exploitation. During the industrial revolution, it was very common to find children working in factories. Since industrialization, children have been seen working in factories, mines, some having their own small business like selling food, flowers, polishing shoes, serving as waiters in restaurants and as domestic servants as well. The most controversial and worst forms of child labour and exploitation included military use of children, child trafficking, organized begging and child

prostitution etc. So these are the various forms of child labour that are being present in today's societies over the world.

The both slums selected show their origin in different situation. Ganesh Nagar was established in 1957 on the government and private land. The Ajanta Nagar was settled or initiated in 2004 it is the rehabilitation slum dweller residing in Jay Malhar Nagar.

POPULATION DISTRIBUTION OF AJANTA NAGAR & GANESH NAGAR

AREA	AJANTA NAGAR
Child Population	38.12
Other Population	61.88

AREA	GANESH NAGAR
Child Population	53.66
Other Population	46.34

DISTRIBUTION OF MALE CHILD POPULATION IN %

AREA	AJANTA NAGAR	GANESH NAGAR
Children below 6 age	15.71	4.55

male		
School going male child	25.13	40.91
Working male child	8.38	22.73
Total child population	38.12	53.66

DISTRIBUTION OF FEMALE CHILD POPULATION IN %

AREA	AJANTA NAGAR	GANESH NAGAR
Children below 6 age female	12.04	4.55
School going female	34.03	40.91

child		
Working female child	4.71	27.27
Total child population	38.12	53.66

COMPARISON OF CHILD LABOUR

AREA	AJANTA NAGAR	GANESH NAGAR
Total child population	38.12	53.66

UNEMPLOYMENT AFFECTING SOCIAL ENVIRONMENT

Name Of Slum	Labour		Total
	Employ	Unemployed	
Ganesh Nagar	45 %	55 %	100 %
Ajanta Nagar	52 %	48 %	100 %

EDUCATIONAL STATUS OF POPULATION

Name Of Slum	% Of Educational Status				Total
	Illiterate	Primary	Secondary	College	
Ganesh Nagar	22	48	26	04	100 %
Ajanta Nagar	42	35	21	02	100 %

Causes of child labour:

- **Over population:** limited resources and more mouths to feed, Children are employed in various forms of work.
- **Illiteracy:** Illiterate parents do not realize the need for a proper physical, emotional and cognitive development of a child.
- **Poverty:** Many a time poverty forces parents to send their children to hazardous jobs.
- **Urbanization:** MNC's and export industries in the developing world employ child workers, particularly in the garment industry.

- **Orphans:** Children born out of wedlock, children with no parents and relatives, often do not find anyone to support them. Thus they are forced to work for their own living.
- **Willingness to exploit children:** This is at the root of the problem Even if a family is very poor; the incidence of child labour will be very low unless there are people willing to exploit these children.
- **Unemployment of elders:** Elders often find it difficult to get jobs. The industrialists and factory owners find it profitable to employ children. This is so because they can pay less and extract more work. They will also not create union problem.

Finding:

Based on the survey data, would like to make the following observations:

- Most population in slums is uneducated and unemployed.
- About 54.94% of the children covered in the listing had received education only up to primary level in both slums.
- Over 14.08% of the children in 5-17 years age group are not attending school. This indicates that the efforts towards complete enrolment and effective retention of slum children need to be strengthened.
- The percentage of child labour involved in hazardous activities was highest in non-notified slums.

Suggestions:

- Problems of the slum can be dealt by little initiative taken by the government, NGOs, Municipal Corporation.
- Elimination of poverty, free and compulsory education, proper and strict implementation of the labour laws, abolishment of child trafficking can go a long way in solving the problem of child labour.
- The World Bank, International Monetary Fund can help in eradicating poverty by providing loan to the developing countries. Various poverty elimination programmes have been introduced by our Government as well for the cause.

- The most essential part in this regard is the effective implementation of the policies and strict enforcement of the labour laws.
- The Government must take strict measures against those employing child laborers in hazardous works and other industries.
- Most importantly the incidence of child labour would diminish considerably even in the force of poverty.
- Developed the education system and facility.
- Compulsory education can help eradicating the problem of child labour up to a large extent.

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